

Real-time energy management of a smart home based on deep deterministic policy gradient

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Abstract—In this paper, we develop a reinforcement learning-based scheme for the real-time energy management of a smart home that contains a photovoltaic-energy storage system. The objective of the proposed scheme is to minimize the electricity supplying cost by appropriately scheduling the storage system on a daily basis. The problem is formulated as a Markov decision process, which is optimized using the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) algorithm. The main advantage of our proposed method compared to optimization-based ones is the ability to obtain effective daily schedules without relying on stochastic variables’ forecasts. In addition, nonlinearities related to the system’s operation can be effectively modeled, without the necessity of approximating them, as in linear optimization-based methods. The results confirm the ability of the DDPG agent to learn from historical data, and then to generalize the obtained knowledge to deal with real-time situations.

Index Terms—energy management, reinforcement learning, deep deterministic policy gradient, smart home, storage system

I. INTRODUCTION

The future smart grid will contain multiple Microgrids (MGs), which are small-scale energy networks comprising Distributed Energy Resources (DER), Energy Storage Systems (ESSs), and Energy Management Systems (EMSs) [1]. MGs appear at various scales, from a single building to a large urban area [2]; their adoption aims to make the traditional energy systems’ operation more efficient, economical and environment-friendly. Hence, large amounts of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) will be placed close to electricity consumers [3]. Despite the potential benefits, the penetration of RES contributes to power variations and imbalances, making the MG’s efficient management a quite challenging task [4].

Smart homes equipped with PVs and ESSs will play a crucial role in the implementation of the smart grid scenario. For several reasons, including government incentives, decreasing installation costs, and environmental awareness, there is a rapid increase in the number of PV installations at residential buildings around the world. The installation costs of ESSs also follow a decreasing trend, making the investment in PV-storage systems popular [5]. ESS is a valuable component because it mitigates the impact of PV generation and demand fluctuations, while it also provides with energy management flexibilities, such as shifting the PV output to cover peak demands [6]. Moreover, it enables MG operators to take advantage of the energy arbitrage; that is to say, when time-varying pricing schemes are applied, such as Time-of-Use

(ToU), the ESS can store energy during low price periods and provide it back to the demand over peak price periods [7].

For the MGs’ economical operation, the proper coordination of their components is required [8]. In MGs comprising conventional DERs, real-time energy management is achieved by performing economic dispatch based on the equal incremental cost-loading principle [9]. However, with the presence of an ESS, obtaining an efficient operation plan for the whole system requires a long term (typically a day) consideration of the time-varying characteristics of electricity prices, RES generation, and load demand, which are stochastic in nature. In this case, the issue of determining a daily operation plan for the MG’s components so that the energy cost is minimized is formulated as a sequential optimization problem that takes into account predictions of the stochastic variables in order to determine appropriate set points for the controllable devices [10].

The Model Predictive Control (MPC) method has been extensively used in the literature for obtaining the on-line management of MGs that contain ESSs ([11] - [14]), and other controllable devices, such as conventional generators in [11], or combined heat and power (CHP) units, thermal storage units and electric vehicles in [12]. In MPC, the on-line management issue is formulated as a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization problem over a receding horizon. Due to the problem’s linear formulation, non-linear characteristics of various devices, such as the efficiency of power electronics are not modeled accurately. This issue is resolved when the MG’s real-time scheduling is modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), which is solved using other optimization methods, such as Dynamic Programming (DP) in [15], or Approximate Dynamic Programming (ADP) in [16]. However, the solution of all methods mentioned above ([11]-[16]), relies on forecasts about the price, RES generation, and demand levels. As a consequence, bad predictions may lead to suboptimal solutions, which in turn result in financial losses.

In the big data era, Reinforcement Learning (RL) can be used to solve MDPs without needing to use prediction models and expensive optimization solvers. RL is the process where an agent learns what to do (action) in a given situation (state) by interacting with an environment to maximize numerical returns (rewards) [17]. Instead of relying on predictions, RL agents can learn how to behave in specific situations by processing historical data, and then to generalize the experience gained

to deal with newly encountered situations.

Several RL methods have been proposed in the literature ([18]-[21]) for the real-time management of MGs' controllable devices. The Q-learning algorithm is applied in [18] for a smart building comprising PVs, an ESS, and a Vehicle-to-Grid system. The proposed algorithm proved to perform better than the MPC algorithm in [14], in terms of energy cost reduction. Q-learning is also used in [19] for increasing the utilization of the MG's wind turbine and ESS, while the Deep Q-learning (DQN) method is applied in [20] and [21] for obtaining real-time schedules of the local DER and ESSs so that the MGs' energy costs are minimized. RL methods have also been implemented for MG topologies that do not contain power sources. For example, authors in [22] develop a Q-learning-based dynamic pricing algorithm for the demand management of a MG aiming to minimize the costs of both electricity suppliers and consumers. Moreover, authors in [23] apply the DQN and the Deep Policy Gradient (DPG) algorithms for scheduling the flexible devices of a smart home with the objective to minimize either its energy cost or its peak demand.

In RL-based approaches, the energy scheduling problem, which is characterized by continuous variables, is modeled as an MDP. However, Q-learning is applicable to MDPs with discrete state and action spaces, while DQN is applicable to MDPs with continuous state spaces and discrete action spaces. As a consequence, these methods suffer from the curse of dimensionality [24]. To resolve this issue, the Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) algorithm is proposed in [24], which is appropriate for continuous state and action spaces. Although the model in [24] considers the presence of ESSs, it does not take into account the energy arbitrage concept. Another machine learning-based attempt to solve an MDP with continuous state and action spaces takes place in [25], where a policy function approximation algorithm is proposed for controlling a smart home's PV-storage system. Policy function is a non-parametric model that is trained based on historical data so that it maps newly encountered states (inputs) to actions (outputs). Although the trained non-parametric model proved to obtain effective ESS schedules, an optimization solver needs to be used during its training process.

The main benefit of formulating the energy management problem as a MDP is the incorporation of the system's nonlinearities, while the main advantage of using RL agents is the ability to solve MDPs without any need for predictions and expensive optimization solvers. Despite these benefits, there is a limitation of works that use RL algorithms compatible with continuous state and action spaces. In this paper, we develop an RL-based scheme for the real-time energy management of a smart home that contains a PV-storage system. Given a ToU tariff, the objective of the proposed model is to minimize the electricity supplying cost by appropriately scheduling the ESS on a daily basis, taking advantage of the energy arbitrage. The problem is formulated as a MDP, which is solved using the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) RL algorithm, which is suitable for continuous state and action spaces.

In the RL methods that have been used in [18]-[24] for en-

ergy management purposes, the RL agents gain experience by processing a whole set of historical data, and then generalize the obtained knowledge on newly encountered situations. In our work, the initial dataset is divided into day-type subsets based on a load demand and PV generation clustering method developed in [5]. Then, a separate DDPG agent is trained for each day-type subset. In this way, the training process becomes more targeted since the agents gain experience from days that have similar demand and generation profiles. Moreover, the generalization process becomes more accurate because any forthcoming day is firstly assigned to one of the predetermined subsets, and then, the agent that has been trained based on the information of that subset is loaded on the EMS for taking real-time decisions for the ESS's set points. Moreover, in order to increase the effectiveness of our method, some common sense rules (heuristics) are used in real-time.

The performance of the proposed DDPG-based method is evaluated by comparing the derived energy cost with the cost when optimal scheduling takes place (i.e., MILP optimization with perfect forecasts of stochastic variables). Our method is also benchmarked against MPC, which has been extensively used in the state-of-the-art, and proved to perform better. With respect to the optimal annual energy cost, the proposed method achieves an error of 2.5%, while the MPC error is 3.27%.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the various smart home's components, and the way the energy scheduling issue is formulated as a RL problem. Section III describes the DDPG algorithm's implementation. Section IV contains a case study for testing the performance of our method, while Section V concludes the outcomes.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND RL FORMULATION

A. System Model

We consider a smart home that contains a PV system, an ESS, a bidirectional inverter, and an EMS, which is responsible for implementing daily energy scheduling subject to operational constraints and economical objectives. The intra-day energy scheduling takes place over a decision horizon of T time slots t of duration Δt . At every time slot, the energy balance at the smart home is described by:

$$P_t^G = P_t^L - m_t^{INV} P_t^{INV} \quad (1)$$

where P_t^G is the power imported from the main grid, P_t^L is the load of the smart home, m_t^{INV} stands for the power transformation losses at the inverter, and P_t^{INV} is the power at the DC side of the inverter, which depends on the generated PV power P_t^{PV} and the power P_t^{ESS} transferred to the ESS:

$$P_t^{INV} = P_t^{PV} - P_t^{ESS} \quad (2)$$

Positive values of P_t^{INV} signify that power is transferred from the DC to the AC side of the inverter; in this case m_t^{INV} is described by the inverter's efficiency $n^{INV}(P_t^{INV})$ ($m_t^{INV} = n^{INV}(P_t^{INV})$), which is a non-linear function of the power passing through the inverter [26]. Negative values of P_t^{INV} signify that power is transferred from the AC to the DC side, and in this case $m_t^{INV} = 1/n^{INV}(P_t^{INV})$. In addition, negative values of P_t^G denote that power is exported

to the main grid, while negative values of P_t^{ESS} signify that the ESS is discharged. The ESS's State of Charge (SoC) SoC_t at t is given by:

$$SoC_t = SoC_{t-1} + m_t^{ESS} (P_t^{ESS}/N_{ESS}) \quad (3)$$

where N_{ESS} is the nominal capacity of the ESS and m_t^{ESS} stands for the charging or discharging losses. When the ESS is charged, m_t^{ESS} is described by the ESS's charging efficiency $n_c^{ESS}(SoC_t)$ ($m_t^{ESS} = n_c^{ESS}(SoC_t)$), which is a function of the ESS's SoC. In case the ESS is discharged, m_t^{ESS} is expressed as the reversed discharging efficiency $n_d^{ESS}(P_t^{ESS})$ ($m_t^{ESS} = 1/n_d^{ESS}(P_t^{ESS})$), which is a function of the discharged power [26]. The ESS's SoC ranges within a minimum SoC_{min} and a maximum SoC_{max} level:

$$SoC_{min} \leq SoC_t \leq SoC_{max} \quad (4)$$

while P_t^{ESS} is bounded by a maximum value P_{max}^{ESS} :

$$|P_t^{ESS}| \leq P_{max}^{ESS} \quad (5)$$

Given the operational constraints in (1)-(5), the EMS targets to determine appropriate set points for the ESS's charging/discharging power to minimize the daily energy cost EC . In this study, it is assumed that the smart home's owner is charged based on a fixed ToU contract. It is also considered that electricity is not sold to the main grid; the decreasing costs of PVs and ESSs motivates the adoption of such a policy, which aims to increase the self-consumption of PV-ESS installations [5]. As a result, the energy cost is given as a function of the electricity imports ($P_t^G \Delta t$, where $P_t^G \geq 0$) and the electricity price c_t during each time interval t :

$$EC = \sum_{t=1}^T P_t^G \Delta t c_t \quad (6)$$

B. RL Formulation

The daily energy scheduling of the smart home's ESS is formulated as a RL problem where an agent is trained through a RL algorithm to learn how to interact with an environment. During training, the agent observes the environment's current state s_t and performs an action $a_t \in A_{s_t}$. The action space A_{s_t} stands for the range of all possible actions that can be taken at state s_t , and it is defined by the rules that govern the environment's transition from one state to another. Depending on the performed action, the environment responds with a reward signal r_t and moves to the next state s_{t+1} , where the agent performs another action, receives a new reward and so on. The sequence of states, actions and rewards, as well as the rules for transitioning from one state to another over a decision horizon, compose a MDP episode. The mapping from states to actions during an episode is defined as the agent's policy π . The objective of a RL algorithm is to train the agent so that an optimal policy π^* is achieved, where the agent's actions at every observed state maximize the total discounted reward R_t^π over a MDP episode of T steps, which is expressed as:

$$R_t^\pi = \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} r_t \gamma^t \quad (7)$$

where $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ is a discount factor that determines the importance of future rewards. When $\gamma=0$, the agent considers

only the current reward, while when $\gamma=1$ the agent weighs equally both the current and the future long-term rewards.

When the smart home's energy scheduling is modeled as a MDP, the system's state $s_t = \{P_t^L, P_t^{PV}, SoC_t^{ESS}, c_t, t\}$ at time slot t is described by a set of variables that include the home's load P_t^L , PV generation P_t^{PV} and ESS's state of charge SoC_t^{ESS} , as well as the electricity price c_t and the time slot's incremental number t . In addition, the agent's taken action $a_t = P_t^{ESS}$, $a_t \in A_{s_t}$ refers to the set points of the system's controllable variable, which is the charging or discharging power P_t^{ESS} of the ESS at every time slot. The system's action space A_{s_t} is defined by the operational constraints in (1)-(5). The reward r_t that the agent receives from the environment at every time interval is described by the opposite of the electricity import cost signifying that higher rewards are obtained when less electricity is imported:

$$r_t = -P_t^G c_t \quad (8)$$

III. DDPG ALGORITHM'S IMPLEMENTATION

DDPG uses four DNNs; a critic, which is a Q-network with parameters θ^Q , an actor, which is a policy network with parameters θ^μ , a target Q-network with parameters $\theta^{Q'}$ and a target policy network with parameters $\theta^{\mu'}$. The objective of the DDPG algorithm is to update the parameters of the four DNNs so that the trained actor represents the agent's optimal policy. The target networks are copies of the original, and they are used for making the training process more stable [28]. The training process takes place by considering MDP episodes where stochastic variables' values are derived from a historical dataset that contains daily load demand and PV generation curves over a long period of time. Specifically, the initial dataset is firstly divided into day-type subsets, i.e., sets that include days with similar load demand and PV generation profiles, and then a separate agent is trained for each day-type subset by using as episodes the days belonging to it.

The process of training an agent based on the data of a day-type subset consisting of Z days is described in Algorithm 1. Firstly, the parameters of the DNNs are initialized (line 1) and a replay buffer of size B is created (line 2). The DDPG algorithm runs for a number of M iterations (line 3); at every iteration, a random episode is selected, and its initial state s_0 is observed (line 4). The main part of the training process takes place within the selected episode (lines 5-14), and consists of the following steps: firstly, the actor observes the system's current state s_t and performs an action a_t to which exploration noise $\Xi(\text{ep})$ is added (line 6). Given the performed action, the environment responds with a reward signal r_t and moves to the next state s_{t+1} (line 7). The transition (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) is stored in the replay buffer, while a mini-batch of N transitions $\left(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, r_\tau^{(i)}, s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, i \in N, \tau \in (T-1) \right)$ is randomly sampled (line 8). Then, a forward pass takes place at the critic for deriving the Q-values of the sampled state-action pairs $(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, \forall i \in N)$ (line 9). A forward pass also happens at the target Q-network for obtaining the Q-values of the pairs $(s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, a_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, \forall i \in N)$ (line 11), where $a_{\tau+1}^{(i)}$ is obtained

by the target policy network (line 10). Then the critic's parameters are updated in line 12 by minimizing the loss function $L(\theta^Q)$, while the actor's parameters are updated in line 13 by maximizing the expectation of the discounted reward $J(\theta^\mu)$. Finally, the target networks' parameters are updated by slowly tracking the parameters of the original networks (line 14).

The derivation of the day-type subsets, required for the DDPG algorithm's training process is based on a clustering method developed in [5]. According to this method, historical data of daily PV generation and load demand profiles are initially separated into seasons. Then, a k-means algorithm is used for obtaining PV generation and load demand clusters based on certain attributes. The total daily PV output is the attribute utilized for defining V PV classes, which correspond to sunny, normal, cloudy days, etc., while the demand level (i.e., high, normal, low, etc.) at different time intervals throughout a day (i.e., 00:00-06:00, 15:00-18:00, etc.) is the attribute utilized for defining D load classes. Given the derived D load and V PV clusters, any day of the initial historical dataset is assigned to one of the $D*V$ day-type subsets that are created.

A separate agent is trained for each subset for obtaining a corresponding policy network. Each agent consists of two DNNs representing the actor and the critic. The actor has an input layer consisting of five neurons, which correspond to the smart home's current state's s_t variables. The critic's input layer consists of six neurons because, besides the current state, it also takes as input the actor's output. Both DNNs have three hidden layers consisting of 128 neurons and relu activation functions. The critic's output layer has a single neuron with a linear activation function, while the actor's output layer has a single neuron with a tanh activation function. Furthermore, for continuous action spaces, exploration is done by adding noise to the action. In our implementation, $\Xi(ep)$ is given by:

$$\Xi(ep) = \begin{cases} 10^{\log \xi_a + |\log \xi_b - \log \xi_a| \frac{ep}{\xi_c}} & \text{if } ep \leq \xi_c \\ 0 & \text{if } ep > \xi_c \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

After the training process is completed, the policy networks can be used for the ESS's real-time scheduling. Any forthcoming day is firstly assigned to one of the $D*V$ subsets. This assignment takes place before the beginning of the decision horizon and can be done by using state identification methods and weather forecasts [5]. Then, the corresponding policy network is loaded to the EMS.

IV. CASE STUDY

For the evaluation of our method, a smart home is considered, equipped with a 2 kWp PV generator, an ESS of 4 kWh nominal capacity, and an inverter. The home is supplied with electricity based on a ToU pricing scheme; the low, medium and high price intervals are reported in Table I [1]. PV generation data for 2018 and 2019 are derived from [29], while load demand data for two years are obtained from [30]. The first year's data are used for obtaining day-type subsets for the training process, while the second year's data are used for testing. By using the k-means algorithm, $D=4$ load and $V=4$ PV clusters are derived, and hence, the initial dataset

Algorithm 1: DDPG agent's training process

- 1: Randomly initialize the critic's and actor's parameters θ^Q and θ^μ , respectively, and set the target networks' parameters equal to them: $\theta^{Q'} \leftarrow \theta^Q$, $\theta^{\mu'} \leftarrow \theta^\mu$.
- 2: Define the size B of the replay buffer.
- 3: for $ep = 1$ to M :
- 4: Select a random day from D , observe s_0 , initialize Ξ_t .
- 5: for $t = 0$ to $T - 1$:
- 6: Observe s_t and perform action $a_t = \pi(s_t, \theta^\mu) + \Xi_t$.
- 7: Execute action a_t in the environment and observe the instant reward r_t and the next state s_{t+1} .
- 8: Store (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in the replay buffer, and sample from it a random mini-batch of N transitions $(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, r_\tau^{(i)}, s_{\tau+1}^{(i)})$, where $i \in N$ and $\tau \in (T-1)$.
- 9: Given $(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, \forall i \in N)$, do a forward pass of the critic for obtaining their Q-values $Q(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, \theta^Q)$, $\forall i \in N$.
- 10: Given $s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}$, do a forward pass of the target policy network for obtaining the actions $a'_{\tau+1} = \pi'(s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, \theta^{\mu'})$.
- 11: Given $(s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, a'_{\tau+1}^{(i)})$, do a forward pass of the target Q-network for obtaining $Q'(s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, a'_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, \theta^{Q'})$, $\forall i \in N$.
- 12: Update the critic's parameters by minimizing $L(\theta^Q)$:
$$L(\theta^Q) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (y_\tau^{(i)} - Q(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, \theta^Q))^2$$

$$y_\tau^{(i)} = r_\tau^{(i)} + \gamma Q'(s_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, a'_{\tau+1}^{(i)}, \theta^{Q'})$$
- 13: Update the actor's parameters by maximizing $J(\theta^\mu)$ using the following sampled policy gradient $\nabla_{\theta^\mu} J(\theta^\mu)$:
$$\nabla_{\theta^\mu} J(\theta^\mu) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (\nabla_{a_\tau^{(i)}} Q(s_\tau^{(i)}, a_\tau^{(i)}, \theta^Q) \nabla_{\theta^\mu} \pi(s_\tau^{(i)}, \theta^\mu))$$
- 14: Update the target networks:
$$\theta^{Q'} \leftarrow \omega \theta^Q + (1 - \omega) \theta^{Q'}, \theta^{\mu'} \leftarrow \omega \theta^\mu + (1 - \omega) \theta^{\mu'}, \omega \ll 1$$
- 15: end
- 16: end

is divided into 16 day-type subsets. Table II contains the parameters' values for the training process' implementation. For determining the daily energy management in real-time, each day in the test set is firstly assigned to one of the predetermined load-PV subsets, before the beginning of the scheduling horizon; then the corresponding agent's trained policy function is loaded to the EMS.

The performance of the proposed DDPG-based method is compared with MPC. According to [5], the medians of load and PV clusters can be used as forecasts, which are required for the implementation of MPC. For example, the predicted load demand for a test day that is assigned to load cluster 3 is given by load cluster's 3 median value. As a benchmark for the evaluation of the two candidate methods is used the smart home's electricity supplying cost when the ESS scheduling is obtained by MILP optimization with a perfect forecast of the demand and generation curves. Nonlinearities related to the ESS's and inverter's operation cannot be modeled when the optimization methods are applied. Instead, the ESS's charging

TABLE I: ToU pricing scheme [1]

Time	0:00-8:00	8:00-18:00 & 22:00-24:00	18:00-22:00
Cost (€/kWh)	0.079	0.109	0.135

TABLE II: Parameters' values

Replay buffer & Mini-batch sizes	$B = 10^6, N = 480$
Episodes' Num., Noise parameter	$M = 8000, \xi_c = 5000$
Noise parameters	$\xi_a = 0.8, \xi_b = 0.1,$
ESS's parameters	$SoC_{min} = SoC_0 = 0.2,$ $P_{max}^{ESS} = 1kW$
Discount factor, weighting factor	$\gamma = 1, \beta = 0.4$

and discharging efficiencies and the inverter's efficiency are considered to be constant taking the values $n_c^{ESS} = n_d^{ESS} = 0.95$ and $n^{INV} = 0.9$, respectively. For a fair comparison of the candidate methods, the same values are considered when the proposed DDPG-based method is applied, despite that nonlinearities could have been modeled.

Table III provides a synopsis of the results; it contains the number of test days belonging to each load-PV subset, as well as the average percentage error of the two energy management methods for each subset and for the whole year. The average error for a subset is defined by the difference between the total electricity supplying cost when one of the candidate methods is applied for the whole set of days belonging to this subset, and the corresponding cost when perfect forecast MILP is used.

DDPG relies on the experience gained during training for achieving effective ESS scheduling. Based on Table III, it preforms, overall, better than MPC, while it is more robust; the error of the various scenarios ranges between 0.69% and 4.6%. On the contrary, MPC relies on stochastic variables' forecasts. As a result, although it has an almost perfect behavior in some scenarios, it is prone to inaccurate predictions, which in some cases, increase the error at high levels. In the following analysis, the robustness of the proposed DDPG-based method is emphasized against the vulnerability of MPC.

Fig. 1 presents the errors of the two methods versus the amount of energy excess of subset's 3-2 days. MPC performs better than DDPG for days with energy excess amounts lower than 1.56 kWh. However, above this threshold, the MPC error increases sharply, while, the DDPG error shows a decreasing trend for days with amounts of energy excess up to 3 kWh. After this second threshold, the DDPG error also increases, remaining, though, lower than the corresponding MPC error. The above outcome is interpreted in the following analysis by examining the ESS's schedules obtained by the two methods for 14/04/19 that belong to subset 3-2.

Fig. 2 compares the ESS's optimal, MPC and DDPG-based scheduling on 14/04/19, when the amount of energy excess (2.23 kWh) is higher than the predicted (1.56 kWh), and the day belongs to the area of Fig. 1 where DDPG performs better. When stochastic variables are perfectly forecasted, the ESS is charged up to SoC 83% during the low price intervals (00:00-08:00) by importing 2.94 kWh from the main grid, while it then provides 1.38 kWh to the load during 08:00-13:00, when the prices take intermediate values. From 11:00 to 17:00, the whole amount of available energy excess (2.23 kWh) is utilized for fully charging the ESS at no cost. Finally, over the peak price period, the ESS is discharged up to the minimum

TABLE III: Synopsis of the results

Day-type subset	Num. of days	DDPG error (%)	MPC error (%)
1-1	5	1.42	9.6
1-2	3	0.69	8.1
1-3	8	0.93	0.5
1-4	3	0.77	3.1
2-1	7	3.47	5.4
2-2	14	1.99	5.5
2-3	26	2.46	1.3
2-4	17	1.15	0.5
3-1	50	2.95	7.25
3-2	59	3	4.73
3-3	63	2.96	2.74
3-4	23	1.67	1
4-1	46	3.1	4.7
4-2	24	2.2	1.17
4-3	10	4.6	4.33
4-4	7	3.7	2.41
Total	365	2.5	3.27

SoC level (20%) providing 3.04 kWh to the demand.

Under MPC, the ESS is charged up to 89% of its capacity over the low price period by importing 3.2 kWh of cheap energy from the main grid, while it is then discharged up to 63% providing 1kWh to the load during 08:00-11:00. MPC discharges the ESS up to this SoC level relying on the fact that the predicted energy excess (1.56 kWh) is enough to fully recharge the ESS at no cost before the peak price period. However, the actual energy excess amount is higher than the predicted (2.23 kWh); part of it is used for fully charging the ESS, and the remaining is injected to the main grid. During peak price, the ESS is discharged up to the minimum SoC level, as in the optimal scheduling case.

When DDPG is applied, the ESS is charged up to a SoC level of 44% during the low price intervals, while it is discharged up to 31% during 08:00-11:00, providing 0.48 kWh to the demand. The ESS is then charged up to 94% before the beginning of peak price by using the whole energy excess amount plus 0.42 kWh of PV energy. Because this additional PV energy is transferred to the ESS instead of the load, it is equivalent to an energy import during the medium price period. Finally, the ESS is discharged up to its minimum SoC level during peak price, providing to the load 2.8 kWh.

The error of the two methods depends on the deviations of the energy amounts transferred to or absorbed from the ESS during the different price periods compared to optimal scheduling. As Fig. 3 shows, regarding the energy quantities that are transferred to the ESS during the low and medium price periods and the quantities discharged from it during the

Fig. 1: DDPG and MPC errors for subset 3-2

Fig. 2: ESS's schedules for 14/04/19

Fig. 3: Synopsis of ESS's schedules for 14/04/19

medium and high price periods, MPC is closer to optimal scheduling than DDPG. However, DDPG achieves a lower error (1.26%) than MPC (6%) because it fully utilizes the available energy excess, which charges the ESS at no cost. On the contrary, MPC relies on the predicted energy excess, which is underestimated, resulting in a waste of energy.

V. CONCLUSION

The main advantage of our proposed scheme compared to optimization-based methods is that it does not rely on stochastic variable's predictions. Instead, different DDPG agents are trained by considering stochastic variable's historical data. The knowledge obtained during the training process is then used to deal with real-time situations. The proposed method has been proved to be effective when applied to a smart home that comprises a single controllable device. In our future work, we are planning to test the ability of the DDPG algorithm in performing effective real-time management on systems that contain multiple energy sources, as well as multiple controllable devices.

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